

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11069498>

INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHNI DALILLASH KONSEPSIYASINING STATISTIK ASPEKTLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada iqtisodiyot, menejment va inson resurslarini boshqarishning dalillarga asoslangan asoslari genezisi tahlil qilinadi va rivojlanish tendentsiyalari aniqlanadi. Inson resurslarini boshqarish sohasidagi qarorlar dalillarini oshirish uchun axborot bazasini shakllantirish manbalari va foydalanish yo‘nalishlari aniqlandi.

***Kalit so‘zlar:** dalillangan iqtisodiyot, ma‘lumotlarning statistik tahlili, inson resurslarini boshqarish, dalillangan boshqaruv.*

СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ДОКАЗАТЕЛЬНОЙ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИМИ РЕСУРСАМИ

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АБСТРАКТ

В данной статье анализируется генезис доказательных основ экономики, менеджмента и управления человеческими ресурсами и выявляются тенденции развития. Для повышения доказательности принимаемых решений в области

управления человеческими ресурсами были определены источники и направления использования информационной базы.

***Ключевые слова:** проверенная экономика, статистический анализ данных, управление человеческими ресурсами, проверенный менеджмент.*

STATISTICAL ASPECTS OF THE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT CONCEPT OF PROOF

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the genesis of the evidence-based foundations of economics, management and human resource management and identifies development trends. To increase the evidence of decisions in the field of human resources management, the sources and directions of use of the information base were determined.

***Key words:** proven economy, statistical analysis of data, human resources management, proven management.*

The relevance of introducing the concept of proof interest in the theory and practice of management domestic human resources enterprises and organizations is due to a number of house of obvious provisions characterizing certain aspects of management theory and practice.

It is obvious that the basis of effective management decisions is complete and reliable information about the object of management, its professional analysis and correction correct interpretation of the results obtained comrade, critical understanding of the previous management experience. Hard Facts and circumstances specific to a particular business enterprise, form the basis of correct no management decision, while like blind copying of fashionable and popular new management decisions, effective for

other enterprises, may lead to costly or irreparable mistakes. However, many managers pay little attention research focuses on the quality of evidence that they use when making decisions. As a result, management decisions are based on the use of so-called best practices, known from history and theory.

The problems of the need and possibility of using formalized methods in the analysis of socio-economic processes and systems are considered by many researchers. The scientific foundations of the discipline “economics” were laid by A. Marshall. He advocated the ability to soberly and clearly identify and analyze the interaction of many economic factors. Other researchers - R. Frisch and J. Tinbergen are known as the creators of econometrics - a science that studies quantitative and qualitative economic relationships using mathematical and statistical methods and models. Awarded for his contribution to the theory of optimal resource allocation. Nobel Prize in Economics 1975 L.V. Kantorovich. In recent years, attention has been given to increasing attention to the use of mathematical and statistical models in the analysis of the likely consequences of decision-making in the field of economics, the study of models that help to better understand the nature of new economic structures that have arisen as a result of reforms, characterize the state of the economy, and predict the consequences of important macroeconomic decisions.

Concepts of evidence-based socio-economic decisions, in particular, “evidence-based economics” “evidence-based management”, “evidence-based engineering and organizational psychology” (“evidence-based economics”, “evidence-based management”, “evidence-based” industrial and organizational psychology”), arose in foreign scientific literature by analogy with the already generally accepted the concept of evidence-based medicine, the emergence of which in 1990 was due to the growing demand skill in critically evaluating medical information to establish its reliability and validity.

2006 Nobel laureate in economics Edmund Phelps explains the need to develop evidence-based economics by the fact that many economic paradigms (examples of which are discussed in the book) are not based on evidence, and also by the fact that

economic policy initiatives often lack preliminary empirical testing, despite the potential for its implementation.

Julian Reiss, developing the methodology of evidence-based economics in her works, introduces three levels of substantiation of economic statements based on evidence. The first level is the measurement level, which analyzes whether statements about quantitative indicators (for example, such as inflation, unemployment, poverty growth) available data and procedures for measuring them. The second level is the level of induction. At this level, hypotheses about the relationship between economic indicators are confirmed by quantitative patterns. The third level is the level of theorizing, at which the correspondence is assessed.

Correspondence of the obtained patterns to the paradigms of economic theory. In recent years, the need for evidence the importance of socio-economic laws and patterns is increasing, indirect evidence of which is the emergence of such concepts as “evidence-based advertising” and “evidence-based human resource management”, “evidence-based public management” (“evidence-based advertising” and “scientifically based” human resource management”, “evidence-based public management”).

The concept of evidence-based management is defined as a point of view on the need to search for scientific justification for management decisions, as a guiding idea for systematic coverage of management problems based on scientific analysis of evidence. Basic postulate the concept of evidence-based management is that it is necessary to search for and possible implement such an approach to relevant (economic, managerial, psychological) practice, in which decisions are made based on the available evidence of their effectiveness, and such evidence is searched, compared, generalized and widely disseminated for use in the interests of social development. Common to all areas is the use of the principle of evidence at any level of decision-making - from public policy to a program for the development of an element of society.

Evidence-based management in accordance with the definition given by the Center for Evidence-Based Management - the first an international organization

established for the purpose of applying evidence-based practice in management - a decision-making process based on critical reflection of the best known scientific evidence and business information. In evidence-based management, decisions are assessed using probabilistic categories rather than intuitive ideas.

According to the most frequently cited definition given in the work, evidence-based management refers to the management of human resources and organizations based on the consistent and coordinated use of four sources of information: the best scientific evidence; organizational facts and characteristics; values and interests of stakeholders; results of examination of practical activities. There are five principles of evidence management.

1. Face unpleasant facts, encourage employees to tell the truth, even if it is the bitter truth.

2. Make decisions based on facts, look for the best evidence and use it as a guide to action.

3. Treat the organization as an unfinished prototype, encourage experimentation, learning by doing, learning on mistakes.

4. Evaluate the risks and disadvantages of recommended solutions, remembering that even the best medicine has side effects.

5. Avoid making decisions based on untested but stable ideas, previous experience, uncritical understanding the experience of successful companies. Let us note that consideration of the aspects of evidence-based management that make up the common definition of this concept and the implementation of its listed principles do not allow us to overcome the subjectivity of those making management decisions. The lack of clear boundaries of the evidence used and a formalized description of the conditions under which certain facts were recorded makes it difficult to use the available data for evidence-based decisions.

In our opinion, the prevailing idea of evidence-based management largely distorts the concept of evidence, according to which “the addition of a new judgment as true to the composition of existing knowledge occurs only when this judgment is either

directly based on the testimony of the senses, or is inferred (proven).), based on the true judgments previously included in the knowledge according to the laws and rules of logic.”

Evidence-based management should be understood as an approach to management in which decisions on the use of management measures are made based on the available evidence of their effectiveness and safety for the development of the managed object, and such evidence is searched, comparison, synthesis and wide dissemination for use in improving management efficiency.

Statistical approaches to the formation of an information base for evidence-based human resource management can be defined by analogy with those used in evidence-based medicine. Namely, the information base of evidence-based medicine is based on recording mass events.

ties and standardization of a set of studied characteristics, the values of which are determined upon the occurrence of events. There are different levels of evidence for decisions depending on the representativeness of the data used to make decisions (from highest to least): data from blind double and triple randomized studies, or data obtained from a meta-analysis of a number of controlled randomized trials; data from controlled randomized trials on a small (in a statistical sense) number of patients; nonrandom small-scale clinical trials on a small number of patients; results of a consensual expert decision.

To form an information base for evidence-based management, firstly, it is necessary to conduct statistical observations of standardized features that determine the impact of decisions in the field of personnel management on the financial and economic performance of the organization; secondly, use mathematical and statistical tools to summarize the results of various observations; thirdly, conduct expert assessment of the results of practical activities of organizations. Based on this classification, most modern research in the field of evidence-based management can be classified as the third level of evidence. The information base for evidence-based decisions in the management of human resources of an organization is the results of

statistical observations. The main sources for replenishing the information base are objective data on the financial and economic condition of public companies, survey data from employees of large companies, data from recruiting agencies. Survey data based on subjective assessments received from company employees. However, with mass observations, survey data can provide more accurate results characterizing the state of staff than such objective characteristics as the average salary, the size of social benefits and packages, staff turnover, etc.

The annual US Federal Employees Survey report uses six indices: four indices, characterizing the development of human capital, the staff engagement index and the overall satisfaction index. In 2012, over 687 thousand employees were surveyed. A questionnaire containing 84 questions was used. The ten-year dynamics of the state of the personnel was analyzed, the state of the personnel of various departments was compared. In Uzbekistan, studies of the state of personnel using questionnaires are not widespread. Today, the source of the formation of an information base for evidence-based personnel management of organizations can be databases of recruiting companies containing information about the qualifications of applicants for vacancies, their professional field of activity, their preferred range of responsibilities, work experience, reasons for dismissal, duration of job search, interests outside of work, marital status, etc. Data on individual priorities when choosing place of work. To assess individual priorities and priorities characteristic of various social and age groups, it is advisable to determine ranks or weight of the most important factors influencing choice. Such factors may include: material benefits, opportunities for career and professional growth, conditions via for self-realization, creativity, initiative, the ability to work in a team, recognition, variety of activities, stability, clarity and the ability to fulfill official responsibilities.

It is advisable to distinguish two main levels of processing statistical data about company personnel and persons applying for vacancies. On the first level directly initial data containing information about individuals is analyzed, the structure of the statistical population is determined, dependencies between observed characteristics are

established, and the values of generalized values are calculated indicators for target observation groups, for example, for personnel of various companies or social and age groups. At the second level, the structure of generalized indicators and dependencies between them. Elements of the statistical aggregate at this level are records of the values of generalized indicators for individual companies and social groups. For example, studies have established statistically significant relationships between the companies' personnel engagement index, which is calculated based on individual results of filling out the questionnaire, and labor productivity. When interpreting data obtained for a particular company, it is necessary to conduct analysis in the following main areas: relevance, representativeness, trends, benchmarks.

1. Relevance of statistical observations - it is necessary to establish to what extent survey data allow us to judge the state of affairs in the company.

2. Representativeness of the data - it is necessary to assess the compliance of the sampling structure with the structure of the company's personnel.

3. Trends in the state of affairs in the company - it is necessary to characterize positive and negative trends in the dynamics of the state of personnel.

4. Benchmarks - comparison with other companies. For a comparative analysis of the state of affairs in different companies, standard questionnaires should be used; in the absence of comparable results, it is necessary to establish standard values for indicators.

In conclusion, we note that the starting point for introducing evidence into human resource management is both critical reflection on best practices and and statistical analysis of mass phenomena in this area. Improving information support for recruitment, creating a system for statistical study of the state of personnel of large public companies and government employees will make it possible to use the methodology and methods of evidence-based human resource management in the interests of increasing labor productivity in the Uzbek economy. To introduce evidence into management practice, it is necessary to continuously improve the qualifications of management personnel, train managers in the methodology and methods of scientific planning and forecasting, instill in them search skills, formalized analysis using new information technologies and correct interpretation of professional information. The development and inclusion in the educational programs of universities of the

educational disciplines “Evidence-Based Economics”, “Evidence-Based Management”, “Evidence-Based Human Resource Management” is a promising direction for developing the analytical potential of management personnel.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Main directions of activity of the Government of the Russian Federation for the period until 2018 [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://www.garant.ru/news/446707/>
2. Materials of the extended meeting of the Government of the Russian Federation on January 31, 2013 [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://president.rf/speeches/17396>
3. Ayvazyan, S.A. Analysis of the quality and lifestyle of the population (econometric approach) [Text] / S.A. Ayvazyan. CEMI RAS. M.: Nauka, 2012. 432 p.
4. Evidence-based economics [Text] / ed. Doctor of Economics Sciences N.V. Pankova; N.V. Pankova, B.V. Korneychuk, A.I. Volkov, D.N. Verzilin, T.G. Maksimova, S.N. Potapychev; FSBEI HPE SPbTEI. SPb.: LEMA, 2011. 171 p.
5. Kleiner, G.B. Econometric dependencies: principles and methods of construction [Text] / G.B. Kleiner, S.A. Smolyak. M.: Nauka, 2000. 104 p.
6. Maksimov, A.G. Evidence-based medicine and healthcare [Text] / T.G. Maksimova, G.K. Maksimov. St. Petersburg: Publishing house of St. Petersburg State University of Economics and Economics, 2001. 159 p.
7. Methodology of statistical research of socio-economic processes [Text] / rep. ed. V.G. Minashkin. M.: Unity-Dana, 2012. 392 p.
8. Petrov, A.A. Analysis of perestroika and reform of the Russian economy using mathematical modeling methods [Text] / A.A. Petrov // Economic science of modern Russia. 1999. No. 4. P. 7-44.
9. Phelps, E.S. Evidence-Based Economics. Series: Frontiers of Growth 2006-10-10 [Electronic resource] / E.S. Phelps. URL: <http://www.project-syndicate.org/com>
10. Reiss, J. Error in Economics: Towards a More Evidence-Based Methodology. Series: Routledge INEM Advances in Economic Methodology, Routledge [Text] / J. Reiss. London, UK, 2007.